

Item	Title in English	Wiki3DRank	N-Wikis	N-Props	N-Words
wd:Q9184	Book of Genesis	21.8700	125	148	168,391
wd:Q8275	Iliad	21.5304	132	113	147,831
wd:Q41567	Hamlet	21.2433	93	136	130,612
wd:Q83186	Romeo and Juliet	20.9841	94	83	162,665
wd:Q480	Don Quixote	20.9273	115	95	110,128
wd:Q8279	Shahnameh	20.7261	99	108	92,005
wd:Q6511	Ulysses	20.6773	72	105	123,428
wd:Q43361	Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone	20.6678	85	80	135,803
wd:Q92640	Alice's Adventures in Wonderland	20.5523	91	84	107,783
wd:Q127149	Lolita	20.4429	63	173	67,843
wd:Q130283	Macbeth	20.3785	72	97	99,014
wd:Q170583	Pride and Prejudice	20.3396	68	123	79,634
wd:Q19786	Old Testament	20.3151	140	60	77,301
wd:Q74287	The Hobbit	20.3062	88	49	148,085
wd:Q8258	One Thousand and One Nights	20.2569	120	42	120,556
wd:Q41542	Dracula	20.2473	68	142	62,963
wd:Q9190	Exodus	20.1433	108	93	54,648
wd:Q161531	War and Peace	20.1038	78	61	109,886
wd:Q208460	Nineteen Eighty-Four	20.0740	86	48	122,550
wd:Q165318	Crime and punishment	20.0696	75	60	112,190
wd:Q60220	Aeneid	20.0588	84	54	110,065
wd:Q140527	The Three Musketeers	19.9853	68	137	50,207
wd:Q150827	Frankenstein; or The Modern Prometheus	19.9030	69	65	95,304
wd:Q326909	Buddenbrooks	19.8900	39	173	62,443
wd:Q46758	Harry Potter and the Deathly Hallows	19.8675	76	43	125,423
wd:Q42040	Revelation of John	19.8595	98	50	83,496
wd:Q16438	The Decameron	19.7643	64	89	65,521
wd:Q37293	Ramayana	19.7137	108	35	92,856
wd:Q147787	Anna Karenina	19.6634	76	69	64,285
wd:Q8269	The Tale of Genji	19.6483	87	61	62,555
wd:Q180736	Les Misérables	19.6159	67	59	80,985
wd:Q164974	Oliver Twist	19.5990	70	68	66,319
wd:Q191838	The Count of Monte Cristo	19.5688	60	94	54,393
wd:Q483034	Robinson Crusoe	19.5634	81	68	55,414
wd:Q183157	The Brothers Karamazov	19.5389	66	45	99,269
wd:Q184742	Metamorphoses	19.5073	60	105	45,844
wd:Q104871	A Midsummer Night's Dream	19.5068	63	66	69,090
wd:Q899334	The Tin Drum	19.4809	33	276	30,653
wd:Q47209	Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets	19.4587	80	43	79,226
wd:Q1396889	Animal Farm	19.4242	84	42	74,635
wd:Q178869	One Hundred Years of Solitude	19.3977	74	24	141,675
wd:Q4577	Book of Job	19.3854	73	72	48,573
wd:Q188538	The Master and Margarita	19.3770	56	56	80,091
wd:Q123397	The Republic	19.2960	78	26	112,496
wd:Q25338	The Little Prince	19.2799	109	33	63,135
wd:Q181488	Gulliver's Travels	19.2651	65	51	67,793
wd:Q86440	The Tempest	19.2644	55	57	71,585
wd:Q8272	Epic of Gilgamesh	19.2484	98	15	144,456

wd:Q46751	Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire	19.2333	78	42	66,347
wd:Q190192	Dune	19.2292	49	64	69,065
wd:Q463108	The Neverending Story	19.1845	31	156	42,723
wd:Q181598	King Lear	19.1646	67	37	81,432
wd:Q523076	Little Women	19.1377	37	216	24,838
wd:Q185118	Treasure Island	19.1134	62	72	43,466
wd:Q70784	Journey to the West	19.0994	58	92	35,925
wd:Q6911	Diary of Anne Frank	19.0917	70	34	78,719
wd:Q46887	Harry Potter and the Half-Blood Prince	19.0734	77	33	72,426
wd:Q174596	Moby-Dick	19.0665	67	47	58,441
wd:Q202975	Wuthering Heights	19.0663	57	64	50,587
wd:Q48244	Mein Kampf	19.0496	81	37	60,189
wd:Q219552	Great Expectations	19.0371	55	46	70,372
wd:Q47598	Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban	19.0178	77	39	58,233
wd:Q41490	Leviticus	18.9899	96	54	33,118
wd:Q206400	The Merchant of Venice	18.9734	52	48	66,919
wd:Q131554	Nibelungenlied	18.9714	58	39	73,495
wd:Q26833	Othello	18.9161	72	38	57,645
wd:Q191380	The Hunchback of Notre Dame	18.9070	52	68	44,472
wd:Q2222	Uncle Tom's Cabin	18.8678	53	36	78,269
wd:Q80817	Harry Potter and the Order of the Phoenix	18.8295	74	31	62,710
wd:Q183565	Twenty Thousand Leagues Under the Sea	18.8262	59	59	41,668
wd:Q214371	The Great Gatsby	18.8236	64	46	48,975
wd:Q79762	The Silmarillion	18.8183	55	36	71,826
wd:Q1219561	Around the World in Eighty Days	18.8099	56	62	41,097
wd:Q217352	Strange Case of Dr Jekyll and Mr Hyde	18.7985	45	90	34,855
wd:Q81689	The Da Vinci Code	18.7907	70	24	81,562
wd:Q8065468	The Adventures of Pinocchio	18.7697	67	49	41,696
wd:Q134425	Tao Te Ching	18.7690	72	44	43,125
wd:Q82464	The Picture of Dorian Gray	18.7638	55	44	55,924
wd:Q191663	The Canterbury Tales	18.7193	56	46	50,317
wd:Q212340	To Kill a Mockingbird	18.7168	52	30	81,839
wd:Q172850	The Name of the Rose	18.7041	53	41	58,536
wd:Q215894	Candide	18.6591	46	39	67,511
wd:Q2870	Gone with the Wind	18.6532	49	29	84,120
wd:Q81240	Judges	18.6490	84	43	33,595
wd:Q28754	Paradise Lost	18.6123	57	36	56,438
wd:Q131719	The Prince	18.6091	72	19	82,696
wd:Q48203	Epistle to the Romans	18.6073	84	32	42,962
wd:Q326914	The Adventures of Tom Sawyer	18.5336	57	40	47,078
wd:Q45192	The Hound of the Baskervilles	18.5320	52	53	39,053
wd:Q182961	Jane Eyre	18.5278	56	39	48,816
wd:Q464928	In Search of Lost Time	18.5140	46	41	55,610
wd:Q221211	Twelfth Night	18.5064	47	47	47,287
wd:Q148643	Oedipus Rex	18.4991	46	37	60,559
wd:Q130295	The Wonderful Wizard of Oz	18.4962	52	48	41,527
wd:Q274744	Sense and Sensibility	18.4813	46	37	59,490
wd:Q241077	Antigone	18.4559	50	40	49,536
wd:Q80038	Ruth	18.4538	85	37	31,629
wd:Q128608	Epistle to the Hebrews	18.4447	79	29	42,679

wd:Q215410	Adventures of Huckleberry Finn	18.4284	55	51	34,607
wd:Q308918	A Tale of Two Cities	18.4166	51	30	61,781
wd:Q193417	Madame Bovary	18.4141	55	38	45,485
wd:Q210784	The Idiot	18.3968	48	35	55,352
wd:Q208002	The Fellowship of the Ring	18.3767	50	34	53,610
wd:Q213019	The War of the Worlds	18.3757	49	35	53,112
wd:Q48922	Orlando Furioso	18.3561	35	34	74,398
wd:Q214132	And Then There Were None	18.3528	43	34	60,670
wd:Q80355	First Epistle to the Corinthians	18.3266	82	32	33,232
wd:Q19871	Waiting for Godot	18.3064	59	24	59,469
wd:Q11678	The Hunger Games	18.2417	49	25	64,315
wd:Q469690	Mansfield Park	18.2274	35	33	67,343
wd:Q1751870	A Game of Thrones	18.2126	53	21	68,362
wd:Q212898	The Magic Mountain	18.2020	40	30	63,224
wd:Q41675	Guinness World Records	18.1776	88	21	40,052
wd:Q151883	The sorrows of young Werther	18.1544	49	37	40,328
wd:Q11829	Hansel and Gretel	18.1423	60	35	34,471
wd:Q29478	Faust	18.1368	52	33	41,780
wd:Q219457	A Journey to the Center of the Earth	18.0712	45	56	26,890
wd:Q208971	1Q84	18.0693	32	84	25,088
wd:Q191949	Brave New World	18.0567	48	25	54,544
wd:Q6113985	Upanishad	18.0546	87	13	56,286
wd:Q185427	The Song of Roland	18.0203	62	26	39,392
wd:Q205875	Tartuffe	18.0060	45	38	36,818
wd:Q332387	The Taming of the Shrew	18.0030	41	39	39,198
wd:Q223880	Emma	17.9946	37	29	57,287
wd:Q233562	The Wealth of Nations	17.9914	53	16	70,914
wd:Q11834	Puss in Boots	17.9880	49	34	37,070
wd:Q183883	The Catcher in the Rye	17.9853	64	19	49,771
wd:Q28306	A Dance with Dragons	17.9833	35	47	37,366
wd:Q240617	Père Goriot	17.9785	40	37	41,245
wd:Q50948	Eugene Onegin	17.9759	54	23	48,557
wd:Q471005	The Mysterious Island	17.9516	40	44	33,906
wd:Q36097	The Trial	17.9385	55	23	45,937
wd:Q726254	The Wonderful Adventures of Nils	17.9183	36	99	16,353
wd:Q329989	Demons	17.9035	40	30	46,905
wd:Q128620	Epistle to the Galatians	17.8915	79	24	29,454
wd:Q192649	The Red and the Black	17.8865	43	38	34,158
wd:Q181937	I Ching	17.8787	57	17	55,707
wd:Q202009	Fahrenheit 451	17.8771	48	30	38,227
wd:Q62407	Mother Courage and Her Children	17.8654	32	38	44,592
wd:Q333179	Persuasion	17.8533	35	32	47,725
wd:Q271764	Lord of the Flies	17.8435	49	26	41,591
wd:Q26505	The Old Man and the Sea	17.8329	72	18	40,053
wd:Q155980	Sirach	17.8191	61	26	32,733
wd:Q237572	As You Like It	17.8018	47	28	38,686
wd:Q6507	Finnegans Wake	17.7776	37	32	41,919
wd:Q11859	The Little Mermaid	17.7496	61	30	26,594
wd:Q123808	Second Epistle to the Corinthians	17.7489	79	28	22,017
wd:Q131115	First Epistle to the Thessalonians	17.7452	76	22	28,735

wd:Q212746	Anglo-Saxon Chronicle	17.7074	48	21	45,458
wd:Q408673	Epistle to the Ephesians	17.6955	79	22	26,315
wd:Q207332	All Quiet on the Western Front	17.6897	48	22	42,716
wd:Q179021	The Alchemist	17.6650	67	19	34,534
wd:Q215983	The Grapes of Wrath	17.6405	51	24	35,255
wd:Q131180	First Epistle to Timothy	17.6268	75	24	23,794
wd:Q233780	Panchatantra	17.6059	55	23	32,942
wd:Q206870	Doctor Zhivago	17.5588	45	19	45,910
wd:Q47228	Kama Sutra	17.5409	81	11	42,162
wd:Q51613	Epistle to the Philippians	17.5347	77	19	26,429
wd:Q565638	Little Dorrit	17.4436	21	25	65,807
wd:Q655717	Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus	17.3589	37	17	50,561
wd:Q131107	Second Epistle to the Thessalonians	17.3222	74	18	23,394
wd:Q131104	Epistle to Philemon	17.2192	77	14	25,704
wd:Q808428	Gospel of Barnabas	16.9396	34	10	59,060